

ISic4409

Fragmentary Latin inscription

Language

Latin

Type

unknown

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

Metcalfe 2019.09.09

Last Change

2020-05-06 - Jonathan Prag created the file based upon Metcalfe's photograph

Place of origin (ancient)

Parthenicum

Place of origin (modern)

Partinico

Provenance

Among material recovered from the area of Partinico

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Partinico, Biblioteca Comunale/Antiquarium Comunale

Physical Description

Fragment of a marble plaque, of which part of the upper border is preserved, but broken on left, right and below.

Dimensions

Height not currently recorded cm

Width not currently recorded cm

Depth not currently recorded cm

Layout

Remains of two lines of Latin letters, with an incised bounding line above

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Deeply incised broad, square v-cut letters, with pronounced serifs. E has very short middle bar; the middle strokes of M start below the top of the outer strokes, and descend to the foot of the line; Q has a pronounced, descending tail; no interpuncts are visible.

Letter heights:

Line 1-2: not currently recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not currently recorded mm

Text

1. [---]em(vac.undefin)q[---]

2. [---]a(vac.undefin)[---]

Apparatus

Text based on photograph

The traces of a letter at the end of line 1 are compatible with O

Translation (en)

Commentary

Believed to be unpublished; full autopsy still required.

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

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Photo M. Metcalfe